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Disparate immune receptor control by p53 sufficient and p53 deficient cancers.

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We used an isogenic PDX model of human triple negative breast cancer in p53 wild-type and p53 deficient backgrounds for discovery of immunologic change resulting from or associated with p53 status in cancer.

1 Results

2
3 We used an isogenic, patient-derived xenograft (PDX) TNBC system to model immunologic change and
4 immune receptor control by p53-sufficient and p53-deficient cancers.

- 5 i. GSE76433
- 6 b. Silencing of Vsig10l in p53 deficient cancers.
- 7 c. Activation of Lrrc7 in p53-deficient cancer.
- 8 d. Silencing of Trem13p in p53-deficient cancer.
- 9 e. Activation of Lrrtm2 in p53-deficient cancer.
- 10 f. Activation of TIGIT in p53-deficient cancer
- 11 g. Activation of Timd4 in p53-deficient cancer.

12 Discussion

13 We used RNA-sequencing here to discover and describe immunity and immunologic change associated
14 with p53 status in human cancer. We identified a large set of immune receptors either activated or
15 silenced that was found to be controlled by p53 status in the tumor. One of these receptors was recently
16 described in germline mutant form as susceptibility of a cancer syndrome (Barrett's Esophagus) (1).

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Citations

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